

THE EXTENT OF THE ANGLOPHONE WORLD AND THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH IN ECONOMIC, SOCIAL AND CULTURAL TERMS

Qayumova Mohinur
Sobirjonova Mukhlisa

Teacher of Denau entrepreneurship and pedagogy institute
Teacher of Denau entrepreneurship and pedagogy institute
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6410088>

Annotation: In this article discusses about the extent of the anglophone world and the importance of English in economics, social and cultural terms

Keywords: Plethora, majority, anglophone world, economic, social and cultural terms

Today a plethora of people of the world speak English as their first and second language, and they are called Anglophones. English-speaking people were considered Anglo-Saxons in the early Middle Ages, they became the majority of the British population, and with the territorial growth of the British Empire, it spread to Asia, Africa, North America, and Australia. After the independence of the British colonies, English became widespread throughout the world. Countries such as the United States, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand use English as their official language. Countries such as India, Iran, and Pakistan use English as a second language.

Firstly, English is now taught as a foreign language in several countries. In particular, it is the official language of one of the international organizations, the United Nations, the Union of African, European, and the South American States, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the Caribbean Community, and numerous other international organizations. According to the latest statistics, English is recognized and used as an official language in 67 independent states, as well as in 27 non-sovereign states. What we do know is that English is a business language. Workers and business people in India, Singapore, Saudi Arabia, Japan, China, and Spain also use English to communicate with people in other countries at work and in trade.

Secondly, the main English-speaking countries are the United States and the United Kingdom, with about 230 million English speakers (native speakers) living in the United States, and it is the largest English-speaking country. In addition, more than 60 million people in the UK speak English as their mother tongue. Another country, Kana, is bilingual in the world, with about 20 million

people using English as a first language and about 17 million people using English as a second language.

English-speaking countries are widespread around the world. Including Ireland, South Africa and New Zealand ... In total, English is the first language used by about 13 million people in these countries. According to statistics, a large part of the world's population today uses English as a first or second language.

In the modern world, with the intensive development of trade, economic and political relations between countries, the method of communication between partners and colleagues is becoming increasingly essential. A foreign language is a vital meaning to establish relationships between entrepreneurs, professionals, and employees of international companies.

Business English is more about interviewing and resume writing. When you enter a business, you need to make presentations, negotiate, answer phone calls, and write service letters, and conduct business correspondence, sign contracts, and much more. It should be noted that English is the language of politics, economics, business, reading, travel, music, and art. Nowadays English has entered our daily lives. We meet English inscriptions on the street, at home, at work, in the city centre, and these can be names of advertisements for companies, training courses, and organizations. For example, the doors of shops and companies have the words "open" or "closed" in English. If you know English, you can read and understand it.

Therefore, an educated person would argue that knowledge of the English language is essential. On the contrary, knowing English can be confusing or embarrassing. English is a source of intercultural communication between people of various languages and cultures. Several linguists and scholars provide meaningful information on the development of competence in intercultural communication. It aims to identify gaps and differences in textbooks identified by college and high school students. It is nicely realized that English is the language of trade and business and in many countries; it is a very important language as a language of diplomacy, international transmission, travel, trade, education, and employment.

I think that people whose second language is English should learn English as raw material, and I can cite the following reasons for this. If you visit the website of any recruitment company in the world today and look for a job, it is clear that knowledge of English is one of the basic requirements in more than 50% of cases and this number will continue to grow. In addition, there are more

professions today where knowledge of English is not only a benefit to the candidate but also a necessary condition for the successful completion of their duties.

You need to know English very well to study at a university that teaches abroad or to study for a master's or doctoral degree. In addition, the common language of articles in foreign journals is English. Good English is always an advantage for success in the international dimension of education.

You can easily travel abroad. If you know the language, you will make a lot of friends from abroad, and you will not need an interpreter during the trip. The doors of the world will be open for you.

Fluency in English is the most important factor that will allow you to move up the career ladder quickly. It offers you countless opportunities to work in foreign companies, work abroad and do business abroad. You can also get a foreign certificate if you know the language.

Your circle will expand, you will make friends, and can expand your worldview with your colleagues or friends from different corners of the world. Everyone has a new perspective.

You can follow world trends without waiting for translation. You will receive advertisements and information quickly; you will be able to understand without the help of an interpreter.

English is one of the easiest languages to learn in terms of grammatical structure. When you learn, it becomes much easier to learn German from a single language family, and Italian and Spanish from sibling families.

More than 80% of the world's websites are in English. You can find any topic in English and there is enough information for that. Don't just get information. You can always get more information.

Reading and understanding books in the mother tongue means getting closer to the culture and understanding the author better. The more books you read in a language, the closer you can get to the culture and lifestyle of that language. It is up to you to experience this privilege.

In short, while there are countless opportunities to learn English, don't delay your dreams anymore. We want to see countries where you dream of an education, a career, or walking the streets. No matter what your dream is, English will always lift you.

